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● Some new distribution records of longicorn beetles (Coleoptera) from a collecting trip in South Yunnan, China

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Abstract: Based on the longicorn beetle specimens collected by the author and Mr. Chao Li from southern Yunnan in mid-May 2023, two genera and six species are newly recorded from China: *Parepilysta* Breuning, 1939, *Clermontia* Pic, 1927, *Distenia fulvipennis murina* Holzschuh, 2011, *Pseudaolesthes aureopilosa* (Gressitt & Rondon, 1970), *Procleomenes humeralis* Niisato, 2008, *Petraphuma boreolaosica* (Viktora & Tichý, 2017), *Parepilysta (Striatepilysta) striatipennis* Breuning, 1949, *Clermontia quadridentata* Pic, 1927. In addition, *Cyrtonops tonkineus* Fairmaire, 1895 and *Demonax leucoscutellatus* (Hope, 1831) are newly recorded from Yunnan Province, and the distribution record of *Carinolesthes pericalles* (Gressitt & Rondon, 1970) from Yunnan is confirmed.

Keywords: longicorn beetles, new records, taxonomy

● 中国云南南部采集之行所见天牛新纪录（鞘翅目）

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摘要: 本文利用作者与李超先生于 2023 年 5 月中旬在云南南部采集的天牛标本, 记录到中国新纪录属 2 个、中国新纪录种 6 个: 帕累皮天牛属 *Parepilysta* Breuning, 1939, 克勒莽天牛属 *Clermontia* Pic, 1927, 鼠灰黄翅瘦天牛 *Distenia fulvipennis murina* Holzschuh, 2011, 金毛伪闪光天牛 *Pseudaolesthes aureopilosa* (Gressitt & Rondon, 1970), 肩原纤天牛 *Procleomenes humeralis* Niisato, 2008, 北寮佩虎天牛 *Petraphuma boreolaosica* (Viktora & Tichý, 2017), 纹翅帕累皮天牛 *Parepilysta (Striatepilysta) striatipennis* Breuning, 1949, 克勒莽天牛 *Clermontia quadridentata* Pic, 1927。此外, 越南须天牛 *Cyrtonops tonkineus* Fairmaire, 1895 和黑尾刺虎天牛 *Demonax leucoscutellatus* (Hope, 1831) 为云南省新纪录, 并确认了脊闪光天牛 *Carinolesthes pericalles* (Gressitt & Rondon, 1970) 在云南的分布。

关键词: 天牛类, 新纪录, 分类学

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Introduction

In mid-May 2023, the author and Mr. Chao Li took a nine-day short collecting trip in southern Yunnan. The specimens of longicorn beetle included some species that had not been recorded from Yunnan, or even from China before. In this paper, part of the identified specimens are introduced: two genera and six species are reported from China for the first time, two species are newly recorded from Yunnan Province, and the distribution of *Carinolesthes pericalles* (Gressitt & Rondon, 1970) in Yunnan has been confirmed.

Material and methods

Material examined in this study is deposited in the private Collection of Jian Sun, Beijing, China (CSJB).

Photographs were taken using a Nikon D7200 camera with a Nikon A-FS 60 mm lens and edited using Adobe Photoshop 2021. Extended depth of field at magnifications was achieved by combining multiple images from a range of focal planes using Helicon Focus Pro v8.1.0.

Taxonomy

Family Disteniidae Thomson, 1861 瘦天牛科

Tribe Cyrtanopini Gressitt, 1940 须天牛族

1. *Cyrtanops tonkineus* Fairmaire, 1895 越南须天牛

Fig. 1A

Cyrtanops tonkineus Fairmaire, 1895: 176. **Type locality:** Vietnam.

Cyrtanops Oberthüri Clermont, 1935: 262. **Type locality:** Vietnam. Synonymized by Pic, 1935.

Cyrtanops wuzhishanensis Wang, 2014: 14, 1123, fig. 0004. **Type locality:** China (Hainan). Synonymized by Hergovits, 2022.

Material examined. 1♀ (CSJB), **China: Yunnan**, Honghe, Jinping, Maandi, Luobodi, 1,393 m, 2023.V.18–19, leg. Chao Li & Jian Sun by light trap.

Distribution. China: Yunnan (**new province record**), Hainan, Guangxi; Vietnam; Laos.

Remarks. Hergovits (2022) recorded *C. tonkineus* from Guangxi, China, and proposed *C. wuzhishanensis* as a junior synonym. Here, *C. tonkineus* is recorded from Yunnan for the first time.

Tribe Disteniini Thomson, 1861 瘦天牛族

2. *Distenia fulvipennis murina* Holzschuh, 2011 鼠灰黄翅瘦天牛

Figs 1B, C

Distenia fulvipennis murina Holzschuh, 2011: 249, fig. 1. **Type locality:** Laos.

Material examined. 2♂♂3♀♀ (CSJB), **China: Yunnan**, Honghe, Pingbian, Daweishan, 2,100 m, 2023.V.13–17, leg. Chao Li & Jian Sun by light trap.

Distribution. China (**new country record**): Yunnan; Laos.

Family Cerambycidae Latreille, 1802 天牛科

Subfamily Cerambycinae Latreille, 1802 天牛亚科

Tribe Cerambycini Latreille, 1802 天牛族

3. *Carinolesthes pericalles* (Gressitt & Rondon, 1970) 脊闪光天牛

Fig. 1D

Aeolesthes (Pseudaeolesthes) pericalles Gressitt & Rondon, 1970: 61, fig. 12d. **Type locality:** Laos.

Aeolesthes pericalles: Hua, 2002: 191.

Carinolesthes pericalles: Vitali, Gouverneur & Chemin, 2017: 53, figs 18a-b.

Material examined. 1♀ (CSJB), **China: Yunnan**, Honghe, Pingbian, Daweishan, 2,100 m, May, 14, leg. Chao Li.

Distribution. China: Yunnan; Vietnam; Laos.

Remarks. Hua (2002) reported the distribution record of “Yunnan” for the first time, and then, Chiang *et al.* (1987) and Li (2009) detailed the distribution records of “Yunnan (Lanping)” [云南 (兰坪)]. However, due to the style of the above articles, no corresponding specimen information was provided, and the latter two articles were written in Chinese, so that Miroshnikov (2019) proposed that “the records in Yunnan, China require confirmation”. Here I present a specimen record from Yunnan, thereby confirming the species’ distribution in China.

4. *Pseudaolesthes aureopilosa* (Gressitt & Rondon, 1970) 金毛伪闪光天牛

Figs 1E–F

Aeolesthes (*Pseudaolesthes*) *aureopilosa* Gressitt & Rondon, 1970: 63, fig. 12f. **Type locality:** Laos.

Pseudaolesthes aureopilosa: Vitali, Gouverneur & Chemin, 2017: 49, 50, figs 15a-b.

Material examined. 4♂♂, 2♀♀ (CSJB), **China: Yunnan**, Honghe, Pingbian, Daweishan, 2,100 m, 2023.V.13–17, leg. Chao Li & Jian Sun by light trap; 1♀ (CSJB), **China: Yunnan**, Honghe, Jinping, Maandi, Luobodi, 1,393 m, 2023.V.18–19, leg. Chao Li & Jian Sun by light trap.

Distribution. China (**new country record**): Yunnan; Vietnam; Laos.

Tribe Cleomenini Lacordaire, 1868 纤天牛族

5. *Procleomenes humeralis* Niisato, 2008 肩原纤天牛

Fig. 2A

Procleomenes humeralis Niisato, 2008: 171, figs 1–6. **Type locality:** Laos.

Material examined. 1♀ (CSJB), **China: Yunnan**, Honghe, Pingbian, Daweishan, 2,100 m, 2023.V.16–17, leg. Chao Li & Jian Sun by sweep net.

Distribution. China (**new country record**): Yunnan; Laos.

Tribe Clytini Mulsant, 1839 虎天牛族

6. *Demonax leucoscutellatus* (Hope, 1831) 黑尾刺虎天牛

Fig. 2B

Clytus leucoscutellatus Hope, 1831: 28. **Type locality:** Nepal.

Rhaphuma semi-scutellata Chevrolat, 1863: 282. **Type locality:** India. Synonymized by Gemminger & Harold, 1872.

Rhaphuma leucoscutellata: Gemminger & Harold, 1872: 2938.

Demonax leucoscutellatus: Gahan, 1906: 286

Demonax leucoscutellatus var. *assamensis* Plavilstshikov, 1927: 107. **Type locality:** India.

Material examined. 2♀♀ (CSJB), **China: Yunnan**, Honghe, Pingbian, Daweishan, 2,100 m, 2023.V.16–17, leg. Chao Li & Jian Sun by sweep net.

Distribution. China: Yunnan (**new province record**), Hongkong, Guangxi; India; Nepal.

Remarks. Hua (2002) reported Taiwan with a question mark, then followed by Kariyanna *et al.* (2017). Though Taiwan was formally recorded by Chen *et al.* (2019), but it was not included in Chou (2004), Löbl & Smetana (2010) and Danilevsky (2020). And we followed Niisato (2020) to delete Taiwan from the distribution list, he clearly wrote: “*Demonax leucoscutellatus* (Hope, 1831) is absent in Taiwan”. Lau (2019) recorded this species from Hongkong, it should be added to the distribution list.

FIGURE 1. **A** *Cyrtonops tonkineus* Fairmaire, 1895, ♀ **B** *Distenia fulvipennis murina* Holzschuh, 2011, ♂ **C** *Distenia fulvipennis murina* Holzschuh, 2011, ♀ **D** *Carinolesthes pericalles* (Gressitt & Rondon, 1970), ♀ **E** *Pseudaolesthes aureopilosa* (Gressitt & Rondon, 1970), ♂ **F** *Pseudaolesthes aureopilosa* (Gressitt & Rondon, 1970), ♀. Scales = 10 mm.

FIGURE 2. **A** *Procleomenes humeralis* Niisato, 2008, ♀ **B** *Demonax leucoscutellatus* (Hope, 1831), ♀ **C** *Petraphuma boreolaosica* (Viktora & Tichý, 2017), ♂ **D** *Petraphuma boreolaosica* (Viktora & Tichý, 2017), ♀ **E** *Parepilysta* (*Striatepilysta*) *striatipennis* Breuning, 1949, ♂; **F** *Clermontia quadridentata* Pic, 1927, ♀. Scales = 5 mm.

7. *Petraphuma boreolaosica* (Viktora & Tichý, 2017) 北寮佩虎天牛

Figs 2C, D

Rhaphuma boreolaosica Viktora & Tichý, 2017: 221, figs 1a-b, 2. **Type locality:** Laos.

Petraphuma boreolaosica: Viktora, 2018: 146, 150, figs 2a-c.

Material examined. 1♂1♀ (CSJB), **China: Yunnan**, Honghe, Pingbian, Daweishan, 2,100 m, 2023.V.16–17, leg. Chao Li & Jian Sun by sweep net.

Distribution. China (**new country record**): Yunnan; Laos.

Remarks. The genus *Petraphuma* consists of 11 species (Tavakilian & Chevillotte 2024) and 4 species were recorded from China (Chen *et al.* 2019). *Petraphuma boreolaosica* (Viktora & Tichý, 2017) is recorded from China for the first time.

Subfamily Lamiinae Latreille, 1825 沟胫天牛亚科

Tribe Apomecynini Thomson, 1860 瓜天牛族

Genus *Parepilysta* Breuning, 1939 帕累皮天牛属

Parepilysta Breuning, 1939: 243. **Type species:** *Parepilysta strandi* Breuning, 1939.

Distribution. China (**new country record**); Myanmar; Philippines; Indonesia; Papua New Guinea.

Remarks. Genus *Parepilysta* includes 13 species of 5 subgenera worldwide, mainly distributed in islands of Philippine, Indonesia and Papua New Guinea, and only the subgenus *Striatepilysta* Breuning, 1949 was known from Myanmar. The genus is recorded from China for the first time.

8. *Parepilysta (Striatepilysta) striatipennis* Breuning, 1949 纹翅帕累皮天牛

Fig. 2E

Parepilysta striatipennis Breuning, 1949: 3, 10. **Type locality:** Myanmar.

Parepilysta (Striatepilysta) striatipennis: Breuning, 1960: 140.

Material examined. 1♂ (CSJB), **China: Yunnan**, Honghe, Pingbian, Daweishan, 2,100 m, 2023.V.13–17, leg. Chao Li & Jian Sun by light trap.

Distribution. China (**new country record**): Yunnan; Myanmar.

Tribe Desmiphorini Thomson, 1860 链天牛族

Genus *Clermontia* Pic, 1927 克勒莽天牛属

Clermontia Pic, 1927: 199. **Type species:** *Clermontia quadridentata* Pic, 1927.

Distribution. China (**new country record**); Vietnam.

Remarks. *Clermontia* is a monotypic genus, and is newly recorded from China.

9. *Clermontia quadridentata* Pic, 1927 克勒莽天牛

Fig. 2F

Clermontia quadridentata Pic, 1927: 199. **Type locality:** Vietnam.

Material examined. 1♀ (CSJB), **China: Yunnan**, Honghe, Jinping, Maandi, Luobodi, 1,393 m, 2023.V.18–19, leg. Chao Li & Jian Sun by light trap.

Distribution. China (**new country record**): Yunnan; Vietnam.

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